

Guiding New Development in the Historic Core Case of Mumbai Metro at D.N. Road Station Precinct

AR. BHAGYASHRI MANOJKUMAR KADU

Abstract:- This thesis focuses on guiding the change in historic core of the City with integrating the new fabric. In a historic core city heritage Structure was Lose their identity. The Core city area is the Financial and Center part of the city led to an outrage worldwide highlighting the need for Linkage between New Development and Old City Core.

Historical structures are important assets in any city. These Old core & centers of cities having social, cultural, economical & historical values in itself. There are important & strong reasons behind their creation. Nowadays City transformations and urban Growth of the city are changing the historic Character and significance of the city due to when The City Core are losing its character & values. It is observed that disintegrated from the existing urban fabric.

This research gives an overview of origin and protection of historical Urban Core areas in the City. Moreover, the study also focuses on the current problems in the Future intervention of historical urban Core areas under the guidance of related laws and regulations in the City. Some effective measures to Guiding New Development in the Historic Core Case of Mumbai Metro at D.N. Road Station Precinct.

Keywords:- Historic city Core, Cultural and Traditional Significance, Urban Form, Urban Identity, Urban Spaces

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Context

The historic core is the essence of a city, the center of its civic, social and commercial life. The factors; which further adds to the vibrancy and vitality of the historic core and also helps the city to build its identity; are the culture, traditions and festivals it celebrates, the methods of celebration and the scale on which it is celebrated. A historic core thus is a unique combination of varied characteristics like socioeconomic life, cultural and traditional aspects with living communities, and their traditional livelihoods.

Core city, is the largest or most important city of a metropolitan area. A core city is surrounded by smaller satellite cities, towns, and suburbs. A central city is usually the first settlement established in an urban region before the outlying districts came into existence, later in history. Central cities often form the regional downtowns of metro areas.

In a city core area recent development does not recognize the potential of Mass transit networks which have a tremendous impact on the urbanization process. When these kinds of movement networks come up, they trigger a whole lot of development especially around the station. After the announcement of such a project transformation starts to take place and many times that transformation is unregulated due to lack of action plans. The area starts losing its sense of character due to the disturbance movement network.

The Mass transit system can act as catalysts for the overall historic core development of the city, if they can be connected to the existing senses of place movement network holistically. These new networks can be placed where Public activities can happen where People can meet and interact.

B. Relevance

Historic preservation is a conversation with our past and our future. It provides us with opportunities to ask, "What is important in our history?" and "What parts of our past can we preserve for the future?" Through historic preservation, we look at history in different ways, ask different questions of the past, and learn new things about our history and ourselves. Historic preservation is an important way for us to transmit our understanding of the past to future generations. History tell us to our past condition for encouragement of new developments.

Our nation's history has many facets, and historic preservation helps tell these stories. Sometimes historic preservation involves celebrating events, people, places, and ideas that we are proud of; other times it involves recognizing moments in our history that can be painful or uncomfortable to remember. (gov, 2021).

➤ Basic understanding about Heritage precincts

Buildings or areas are being listed because of their historical value and associations with great personalities or events. Heritage buildings are basically a link between the past and present which gives cultural identity, idea of architecture, social, economic and cultural values of the past (Kathpalia, Heritage Buildings and Precincts, Mumbai, 2002). These are being listed to make available for research and to leave a record for future generations. Listing is a continuous process which categorizes buildings in three categories: Grade I, Grade II and Grade III structures. Historic precincts consist of large concentrations of heritage buildings of architecture, historic value and streets capes. Elements which are conserved in precincts are layout of streets, open spaces, roof forms, skyline and urban character.

➤ *Need of insertion of new activities in the Historic City*

In India all cities are Growing Faster and add a new Proposal in the City Core area Like Transit Corridor, Bridges, etc. the changing social structure, the changing needs in physical and economic infrastructure its creation of increasing tension between Conservation and Development. Cultural value of the City which are extremely important or the present and future of Society.

➤ *Significance of Historic Core*

Significance of Historic Core recognizes the dynamic nature of cities and integrates urban Development within a wider urban context, considering the spatial organization and connection, the natural features and settings, and the social, cultural and economic values of historic areas. It lacks an effective approach to link Urban heritage Core of the City. Urban morphology focuses on the contextual urban fabric and the interrelation between components instead of individual monuments, so it is considered as a powerful tool in Urban Development.

➤ *Importance of Historic Core*

Over the past decade, the Quality of the Historic Core City has a Commercial Centre of the city it is become a significant factor of the transportation Planning and design for Indian Cities. The Transformation in an existing City should be sensitive and focuses on improving the experience of New Activities. The Historic Core have a interesting areas within the Urban Fabric of Cities. In new development the Historic core area are loss their Urban Fabric.

C. Urban design Issues & Concerns

- Transit corridors are a primary element in the city for the development process. These are major issues related to the impact of the existing heritage core area.
- Transit corridors are a change in existing urban form in the city.
- Changes in movement patterns.
- Change in the walkable patterns which affects the heritage precincts.
- High degree of UN regulated transformation in the informal sector which affects overall built form.
- Some places have a historic identity that time they were built. During Urbanization they place use in different manners and they change their identity.
- Increasing population growth, encroachments by vendors in the core area, over the use of space, changes in the land use deteriorate the identity of the place.
- Increasing traffic congestion and haphazard parking the traditional urban fabric of the historic core and hence it is losing traditional urban form. Illegal bazars hawkers acquired those areas. The original intent of the area has been changed. Due to lower price of goods rather than local shops, vanishing such places is difficult.

D. Research Questions

- What are the historic features of the Core city that are not identified by current New Development?
- How could the guidelines be modified to better recognize the Historic Core?
- What are the Recommendations been reflected and implemented in the city urban development with respect to historic identity?
- How can the Guiding the change of a historical precinct be sustained and enhanced culturally, socially, economically and spatially through the dynamics of change and can the city be revived?

E. Hypothesis

Guiding the Change in Historic core areas have to conserve and revive traditional patterns to engage local communities in new approaches towards a transit oriented sustainable future of the city.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Fig. 1: Research Methodology

This research is based on a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. In order to respond to the first objective and extensive research on literature about Urban Development and Urban Conservation was completed. It gave the opportunity to observe historic Core City areas from a different perspective and obtain a more view about Urban New Form. In addition, Three Case Studies of historic core cities were examined in this research UNESCO World Heritage Site and it was possible to evaluate the new approach of UNESCO about historic Core cities.

This study focused on a Metropolitan area with a Historic core. At first, the historical background of the city and the Urban Interventions that were Developed Transit corridors in the Core area that can impact the Project affected area. This Study provided data that made it possible to identify the changes in the City Core that occurred in the area and the impact they had in the city.

III. CONCLUSION

The major role played by core city area development like transit corridor maintain the growth of heritage structure, economic and local people. Thus, the architectural language should fit into its historic character and specification of facilities that is already absorbed by the users and operators.

Also, for proper functioning of the historic core of the city it is essential that the activities planned should be in proper sequence and its maintenance are major crucial aspects to be considered. The planning needs to take the initial effort of retaining some part of the built fabric of the City. It has been the economic strength of the city through the past and present contributing to the Future image of the city which hence connects historic glory with people, therefore making it more inviting.

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